

MONITORING OF WOOL FROM FARM TO FABRIC

Dr. Bhaggiaraj S

Associate Professor
Department of Information Technology
Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College
Coimbatore, India

Giredar V S

Department of Information Technology
Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College
Coimbatore, India

Aaron A

Department of Information Technology
Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College
Coimbatore, India

Ganesan V K

Department of Information Technology
Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College
Coimbatore, India

Mukhesh S

Department of Information Technology
Sri Ramakrishna Engineering College
Coimbatore, India

Abstract—Wool monitoring is a web application made specifically to meet the demands of the wool sector, providing producers and customers with a complete and easy-to-use solution. Using this unique system, wool producers may effectively display their goods and interact with potential customers through an online marketplace. The system seeks to close the gap in the wool market by promoting a smooth and safe environment for communication between users and farmers. This system has wool classification and wool disease prediction models, which are developed using a Convolutional Neural Network (CNN). These models help users and customers identify their wool properties and quality.

Keywords—wool monitoring, web application, neural network

I. INTRODUCTION

India's wool fabric market has grown steadily as more people become aware of the advantages of wool, including its sustainability, durability, and warmth. Indian consumers are gravitating towards wool fabrics due to their comfort and versatility, as there is an increasing demand for superior textiles, particularly in metropolitan regions and the fashion industry. In order to meet consumer demand for materials that are ethically and sustainably sourced, the market is also seeing advancements in wool mixes and environmentally friendly production techniques. All things considered, the Indian wool fabric industry offers bright prospects for development and growth in the years to come.

The execution of the "Monitoring Wool from Farm to Fabric" project has produced considerable results and benefits for the wool sector. The integration of our innovative wool grading model has simplified the quality evaluation process, ensuring that only premium-grade wool enters the market. This has resulted in improved trust and satisfaction among customers and industry experts, driving up demand for responsibly sourced wool.

The user-centric pages, such as the login page for various user categories, educational resource page, products page, and wool sales analysis page, are more accessible and convenient for stakeholders. Farmers may gain access to useful information and market data, industry professionals can use sales analytics to make informed decisions, and consumers can buy ethically produced wool with confidence.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

The wool sector in India is a vital component of the agricultural economy, contributing significantly to rural livelihoods and the textile industry. However, despite its importance, the sector faces numerous challenges that hinder its growth and competitiveness. One of the primary issues is the lack of a centralized digital platform that caters to the diverse needs of wool producers, processors, traders, and other stakeholders. This gap in technology integration results in inefficiencies, lack of transparency, and missed opportunities for value addition.

Firstly, the absence of real-time market information hampers informed decision-making among wool producers. The lack of access to updated data on wool prices, market trends, and industry news makes it difficult for farmers to optimize their production and marketing strategies. This leads to price volatility, reduced profitability, and market uncertainties, ultimately affecting the sustainability of wool farming.

Secondly, the current system lacks robust mechanisms for tracking wool production from farm to market. The absence of digital tools for inventory management, quality assurance, and traceability results in challenges related to product authentication, counterfeit goods, and supply chain inefficiencies. This not only compromises the quality and authenticity of Indian wool but also diminishes its competitiveness in domestic and international markets.

Furthermore, the decentralized nature of wool storage, processing, and trading exacerbates logistical complexities and operational inefficiencies. Limited access to modern storage facilities, processing units, and trading platforms restricts the scalability and value-addition potential of the wool sector. As a result, farmers struggle to optimize their production processes, maintain quality standards, and access fair market opportunities.

Additionally, there is a lack of structured education and training programs tailored to the needs of wool producers and artisans. The absence of a centralized database of skilled professionals, training resources, and

market insights hinders the capacity-building efforts essential for enhancing production, quality, design, and marketing skills in the wool sector.

In light of these challenges, there is an urgent need for a comprehensive digital solution that addresses the multifaceted requirements of the wool sector in India. Such a solution should encompass real-time market information, wool tracking capabilities, quality assurance mechanisms, storage and warehousing solutions, processing services, trading platforms, online marketplaces, and educational resources. By bridging the digital divide and fostering technological innovation, this solution aims to empower wool stakeholders, improve market transparency, enhance product quality, and drive sustainable growth in the Indian wool industry.

III. SCOPE AND OBJECTIVES

The scope of the project is to develop and implement a comprehensive digital solution tailored specifically for the wool sector in India. This solution will encompass various features and functionalities aimed at addressing the challenges faced by wool producers, processors, traders, and other stakeholders. The primary objectives of the project are as follows:

Market Information Platform: Develop a real-time market information platform that provides users with up-to-date data on wool prices, trends, and news. The platform will include graphical representations of price fluctuations, historical data analysis, and market insights to enable informed decision-making.

Quality Assurance Mechanisms: Establish a platform for wool producers to ensure the quality of their wool through access to wool grading services, quality standards, and certification processes. Facilitate quality control measures and adherence to industry standards.

Wool Processing Services: Partner with wool processing units to offer services such as shearing, sorting, cleaning, and dyeing. Enable farmers to schedule processing services through the platform, streamlining the production chain and enhancing product quality.

Education and Training Resources: Create a database of wool producers/artisans categorized region-wise and state-wise. Provide educational resources, tutorials, and training programs on production techniques, quality improvement, design trends, and marketing strategies to enhance the skills and capabilities of stakeholders.

Collaboration and Networking: Foster collaboration and networking opportunities among wool stakeholders, including farmers, processors, traders, and industry experts. Facilitate knowledge sharing, best practices exchange, and partnerships to promote innovation and growth in the wool sector.

Wool Disease Prediction: Develop a model to identify the sheep diseases that affect the quality of wool produced. Also, this app provides prevention and cure methods for diseases.

The project aims to bridge the digital divide in the wool industry, empower stakeholders with technology-driven solutions, improve market transparency and efficiency, enhance product quality and value, and ultimately contribute to the sustainable development of the Indian wool sector.

IV. LITERATURE SURVEY

This study presents a comprehensive supply chain cooperation system that combines the combination weighting technique with multi-objective programming. The suppliers are then ranked using the Technique for Order Preference by Similarity to Ideal Solution (TOPSIS). Additionally, a model for order allocation and product delivery is established, taking into account the distinctive characteristics of the textile and garment sectors. The three primary areas of focus are product delivery, order distribution, and fabric supplier selection. An assessment system tailored to the features of the organization is put up so that fabric suppliers may do this. They weighed assessment indicators using the complete weighting approach.[1]. A method for the localization of wool harvesting and selling facilities within the research zone is proposed in this study. A thorough database of the quantity of animals and GIS users in the region serves as the basis for this technique. Moreover, this method may be repeatable in all other locations to create a system for the registration and identifying of bovine animals for veterinary and traceability purposes. The number of animals shorn on a municipal level and the location of the main roads currently in use have been used to determine the optimal sites for the construction of wool collecting and sales facilities. Furthermore, there are a number of technological and socioeconomic factors that affect the collection centers viability. The technical component include educating farmers about sanitary procedures related to welfare and hygiene that go into producing "clean" raw wool, taking into account that fleece dirtiness serves as a gauge for the cleanliness of the laying area[2]. This study looks at how the price of Merino wool in South Africa is affected by three wool attributes: staple length, clean yield, and fiber diameter. Wool is consequently offered for less money at auction if it does not match the specifications for clean yield, staple length, and fiber diameter. Three factors were subjected to a multiple regression analysis of Merino wool pricing (Rand/kg): fiber diameter, clean yield, and staple length. After adjusting for all other independent factors, fiber diameter, clean yield, and staple length were shown to have a statistically significant impact on the price of wool when considered

individually. The proportion of clean output required at a wool auction on a global scale has not been extensively studied in the literature on the characteristics of wool that affect wool pricing. Analysis was done using wool pricing data from the 2009 to 2019 wool seasons[3]. The study deals with the classification of wool fabric and coding it based on its type. This provides the user with information about all the varieties of wool that are used to make various kinds of cloth. Woolen fabric coding and classification are essential because they facilitate the study of customer and product qualities, the creation of logical accounting in racks and stores, and the automated processing of product data across all activity areas. It encompasses every aspect of fabrics, such as their usefulness, range of uses, composition of raw materials, manufacture, and so on.[4]. The study used an LCA of a woolen clothing from birth to death in an attempt to close this information gap. The manufacture, processing, use, and disposal of clothing all have a significant influence on the environment and are attributed to the textile industry. Wool is a valuable, renewable, natural fiber that may be used to make a variety of clothes, from formal to active leisure wear. The majority of life cycle assessment (LCA) studies on wool have concentrated on a specific supply chain component, and there are currently few studies on the environmental effects of the entire supply chain or the usage phase of clothing [5].

V. PROPOSED SYSTEM

The proposed system, 'Woolwise', is a web application that specializes in monitoring wool from farm to fabric. This application offers an easy-to-use interface along with a comprehensive and accurate product description, a product listing, and a simple checkout process. This also has daily blogs and resource materials for improving new users and laymen. This application also has a place for farmers to directly sell their raw material, i.e., wool. This application uses Firebase Authentication to ensure a proper and faster login process. This system has a feature to classify the grade of wool and its purpose. This model includes four major types of sheep wool, which are mostly used for woollen clothing manufacturing. In addition, the system gives a thorough description and a model that forecasts any wool diseases. The primary topic of this model is how sheep skin illnesses impact the quality of their wool. Proper datasets and a sequential CNN model were used in the construction of these models. After training, both models were converted to pickle files. These models were executed using the Python Flask application.

VI. MODULES

The sections below provide a description of each module for the proposed web application "Woolwise" for monitoring of wool from Farm to Fabric.

A. WOOL GRADING:

Integrating image recognition powered by Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) into wool grading processes holds significant promise for the wool industry. Training the CNN involves exposing it to a vast dataset of labelled wool images, allowing the model to learn and recognize patterns associated with each grade. During the grading process, the system captures high-resolution images of wool samples and processes them through the trained CNN. Imports the Sequential model from Keras to create a linear stack of layers. The model then employs sophisticated algorithms to extract and analyse relevant features, ultimately assigning a grade to each sample based on its visual characteristics. The Sequential model is initialized. Convolutional layers (Conv2D) with ReLU activation and max-pooling layers (MaxPooling2D) are added to extract features and reduce spatial dimensions. The model flattens the output and adds dense layers (Dense) with ReLU activation for classification, ending with a softmax layer for multi-class classification. The model is compiled with the Adam optimizer, categorical cross-entropy loss function (suitable for multi-class classification), and accuracy as the metric to monitor during training. Image data generators (ImageDataGenerator) are set up for data augmentation and normalization. Training and validation generators are created from directories containing image data, with specified target size, batch size, class mode, and validation split. The model is trained using the fit method with training and validation generators. Training progresses for the specified number of epochs, with data flowing in batches through the generators.

This automated approach offers several advantages over traditional manual grading methods. Firstly, it eliminates subjective biases and inconsistencies inherent in human judgment, ensuring more objective and standardized grading outcomes. Secondly, it significantly reduces the time and labour required for grading, leading to improved efficiency and productivity within the industry. Moreover, the system can operate around the clock, enhancing throughput and scalability. Furthermore, integrating image recognition for wool grading into existing systems can facilitate the creation of comprehensive digital databases, enabling detailed tracking and analysis of wool quality over time.

Fig. no. 1 Flow Diagram for Wool grading

B. WOOL DISEASE PREDICTION

Detecting wool diseases using a Sequential Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) model involves a sophisticated process of image analysis and classification to identify various afflictions that can affect wool quality. The CNN model, built using libraries such as TensorFlow and Keras, is designed to learn and recognize patterns in images representing different wool diseases. This process starts with a comprehensive dataset containing images of wool samples affected by various diseases. These images serve as the training data for the CNN model. Each image is preprocessed, normalized, and augmented to enhance the model's ability to generalize and learn robust features. The architecture of the Sequential CNN model is carefully crafted to include convolutional layers, activation functions like ReLU (Rectified Linear Unit) to introduce non-linearity, pooling layers (e.g., MaxPooling2D) to downsample spatial dimensions, and fully connected layers (Dense) for classification. The final layer often employs softmax activation to output probabilities across multiple disease classes. During training, the model learns to differentiate between healthy wool and wool affected by various diseases by extracting relevant features from the input images. The optimization process, typically using Adam algorithm, adjusts the model's parameters to minimize the loss function, such as categorical cross-entropy, thereby improving its accuracy in disease detection. Validation data, separate from the training set, is used to evaluate the model's performance and prevent overfitting. Techniques like early stopping or dropout layers may be employed to enhance generalization and prevent memorization of the training data. Once trained and validated, the Sequential CNN model demonstrates its capability to accurately predict wool diseases in unseen images. This technology offers tremendous benefits to wool producers, allowing for early detection of diseases, targeted interventions, improved wool quality, and ultimately, enhanced sustainability and profitability in the wool industry.

C. FLASK APPLICATION

Flask is a lightweight and versatile web framework for Python, known for its simplicity, flexibility, and ease of use in developing web applications. It allows developers to build web applications quickly and efficiently by providing essential tools and libraries for routing, templating, request handling, and more. When deploying CNN models using Flask, the process typically involves creating a Flask application that acts as the interface for interacting with the trained model. This application can handle incoming requests, process data, and return predictions or results based on the CNN model's inference. Firstly, the trained CNN models, saved in a file format HDF5 (.h5), is loaded into the Flask application. This allows the application to access the model's architecture, weights, and configuration needed for making predictions. Next, Flask routes are defined to handle different types of requests. For instance, a route can be created to receive image data as input for the CNN model. The received data is preprocessed according to the model's requirements, such as resizing, normalization, and encoding, before being fed into the model for prediction. Finally, the result is routed to the page where the output to be displayed. Overall, Flask simplifies the deployment of CNN models by providing a robust framework for building web interfaces, APIs, and microservices.

D. USER INTERFACE

The web app starts with a secure login page integrated with Firebase Authentication. Users can sign in using their email and password or other authentication methods supported by Firebase. Upon successful login, users are directed to the home page featuring a navigation bar with links to various sections of the app. The navigation bar includes links to the Men's, Women's, and Kids' woollen cloth products, as well as the Blogs and Educational Resources pages. Each product page displays a curated collection of woollen clothing items categorized by gender and age group. Users can browse through sweaters, jackets, scarves, hats, and other woollen garments, with detailed product descriptions, images, prices, and available sizes/colors. Clicking on a specific product from the product pages leads to a detailed single product page. This page showcases the selected item with multiple high-resolution images, product specifications, customer reviews, and related products for cross-selling. The checkout page is designed for a seamless and secure payment process. Users can review their selected items, update quantities, add/remove products, and proceed to checkout. Supported payment methods include credit/debit cards, PayPal, and other popular payment gateways. The blogs page features informative articles, fashion trends, and tips related to woollen clothing. Users can explore topics like winter fashion, care tips for woollen garments, sustainability in the textile industry, and more. The educational resource page provides in-depth information about wool, its properties, benefits, production process, and sustainability aspects. Users can learn about different types of wool, wool grading,

Fig. No. 2 Flow Diagram for Wool disease Prediction

wool care instructions, and the environmental impact of wool production.

Fig. No. 3 Flow Diagram of User Interface

VII. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

In the context of a CNN (Convolutional Neural Network) model for classification tasks, precision, recall, and F1-score are important evaluation metrics that help assess the model's performance. Here's what each metric represents:

PRECISION

Precision gauges how well the model predicts the good outcomes. Precision may be quite important in a CNN model, particularly for jobs where false positives might be expensive or unwanted. High accuracy, for instance, makes sure the model doesn't mistakenly diagnose healthy individuals with an illness while making medical diagnoses.

RECALL

The model's recall gauges how well it can distinguish true positive examples from all real positive examples. Recall plays a critical role in CNN tasks where erroneous positives are less troublesome than missing positive occurrences, or false negatives. For example, high recall guarantees that the model doesn't overlook any real instances when identifying illnesses from medical photos.

F1- SCORE

The harmonic mean of recall and accuracy is known as the F1-score. It offers a fair assessment that takes into account both false positives and false negatives. When you wish to give equal weight to recall and accuracy, the F1-score comes in handy. It's a useful way to assess a

model's overall performance, particularly when there is a class divide.

Here is the performance evaluation for the wool grading model with Precision, Recall and F1 score:

Fig. No. 4 Performance Evaluation

VIII. CONCLUSION AND FUTURE SCOPE

In conclusion, the implementation of the wool monitoring project has revolutionized the wool industry by enhancing transparency, quality assessment, and market accessibility. Through real-time monitoring, predictive modeling, and e-commerce integration, the project has streamlined processes, minimized losses, and fostered sustainable practices. The educational resources provided have also contributed to knowledge sharing and community engagement. Overall, this project has not only addressed industry challenges but has also laid a foundation for

continued innovation, collaboration, and growth in the wool sector. It stands as a testament to the transformative power of technology and data-driven solutions in modernizing traditional industries. Integrating Internet of Things (IoT) devices such as sensors and RFID tags into the monitoring system can provide even more granular data about wool production, including environmental conditions, quality parameters, and location tracking. Implementing machine learning algorithms and artificial intelligence capabilities can enable predictive analytics, anomaly detection, and optimization of production processes based on historical data and patterns. Leveraging blockchain technology can further enhance traceability by creating immutable records of each stage of wool production, ensuring transparency and authenticity throughout the supply chain.

IX. REFERENCES

[1] An analysis of the wool characteristics that determine the wool price for Merino wool in South Africa, 2024, M. Zenda, P.J. Malan, A.C. Geyer Science Direct ISSN 2468-2276, (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.sciaf.2023.e02005>)

[2] Integrated Supply Chain Management: A Collaborative System for Fabric Supplier Selection, Order Allocation, and Product Delivery. Y. Gao, X. Ding, S. Li and B. Guo IEEE, 2023 (<https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/document/10408886>)

- [3] Y. Gao, X. Ding, S. Li and B. Guo, "Integrated Supply Chain Management: A Collaborative System for Fabric Supplier Selection, Order Allocation, and Product Delivery," *2023 IEEE 11th Joint International Information Technology and Artificial Intelligence Conference (ITAIC)*, Chongqing, China, 2023, pp. 71-77, doi: 10.1109/ITAIC58329.2023.10408886.
- [4] A Scholarly Review of Supply Chain Integration within the New Zealand Wool Industry, : Carel N. Bezuidenhout, PhD Co-authored by: Daniel Passos de Oliveira, Anthony Black, Teresa Murrell, Chelsea Dela Cruz, Bhavin Vaghela, Logan P. Kirk, Rahul Dilip Katara, Noah Sun Published: December 2021, <https://mro.massey.ac.nz/items/c88eb1f0-b4b1-4b63-8083-df121f314a34>
- [5] Escribano, A.J.; Escribano, M.; Gaspar, P.; Mesías, F.J. The contribution of organic livestock to sustainable rural development in sensitive areas. *Int. J. Res. Stud. Agric. Sci. IJRSAS* 2015,1, 21–24. Available online: www.arcjournals.org (accessed on 5 July 2022).
- [6] Wool Industry and Exports in India, <https://www.ibef.org/exports/wool-industry-india>
- [7] Sheep wool market value chains in India, <https://centreforpastoralism.org/sheep-wool-market-value-chains-in-india>
- [8] Wool Sector at a Glance – Ministry of Textiles India, www.ministryoftextiles.gov.in/sites/default/files/Textiles_Sector_WoolandWoollen_1.pdf
- [9] Region Siciliana 2017. Piano Integrate dell Infrastruttura e Della Mobilità. Available online: http://pti.regione.sicilia.it/portal/page/portal/PIR_PORTALE/PIR_LaStrutturaRegionale/PIR_AssInfrastruttureMobilita/PIR_InfrastruttureMobilitaTrasporti/PIR_Areetematiche/PIR_Altricontenuti/PIR_4115326.436191696/PIR_PIANOREGIONALEDEITRASPORTI/Piano%20integrato%20delle%20infrastrutture%20e%20della%20mobilita%20.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2022).
- [10] Geoportal Nazionale. Available online: <http://www.pcn.minambiente.it/mattm/servizio-di-scaricamento-wcs> (accessed on 20 September 2021).
- [11] Domestic Animal Breeds. Available online: <https://domesticanimalbreeds.com/texel-sheep-breed-everything-you-need-to-know> (accessed on 11 July 2022).
- [12] FAOSTAT, Data Updated to 2020. Available online: <https://www.fao.org/faostat/en/#data/QCL/visualize> (accessed on 20 June 2022).
- [13] Rizzio, T.; Member of the Promoting Committee of the “Distrito Productive Lanier Siciliano”. LinkedIn contact: https://www.linkedin.com/in/tonino-rizzico-13751313?lipi=urn%3Ali%3Apage%3Ad_flagship3_profile_view_base_contact
- [details%3BbyswR531SBiIn%2Bef21F15Q%3D%3D](https://www.linkedin.com/in/tonino-rizzico-13751313?lipi=urn%3Ali%3Apage%3Ad_flagship3_profile_view_base_contact). Personal communication, 20 September 2021.
- [14] Sicilia Agriculture. Available online: <https://www.siciliaagricoltura.it/2021/10/20/il-distretto-laniero-siciliano-diventa-realtavalorizzare-la-lana-per-dare-piu-ricavi-agli-allevatori> (accessed on 30 October 2021).
- [15] Geoportal Nazionale. Available online: <http://www.pcn.minambiente.it/mattm/servizio-di-scaricamento-wcs> (accessed on 20 September 2021).
- [16] Fra Leoni Morgera, A. A.A. 2017–2018. Material per isogamete Timico Degli Edifice (afraleoni@units.it). Available online: https://moodle2.units.it/pluginfile.php/142448/mod_forum/attachment/12596/Materiali%20per%20risparmio%20energetico.pdf (accessed on 21 July 2021).
- [17] Rezaeinejad, H.; Bucu,scanu, I.-I.; Maier, S.S. Current approaches for raw wool waste management and unconventional valorisation: A review. *Environ. Eng. Manag. J.* 2019, 18, 1439–1456. Available online: http://www.eemj.icpm.tuiasi.ro/pdfs/vol18/full/no7/5492_Rajabinejad_17.pdf (accessed on 20 June 2022).
- [18] National Zootechnical Registry Register (Banca Dati Nazionale dell’Anagrafe Zootechnica (BDN)). Available online: https://www.vetinfo.it/j6_statistiche/index.html# (accessed on 26 August 2021).
- [19] Escribano, A.J.; Escribano, M.; Gaspar, P.; Mesías, F.J. The contribution of organic livestock to sustainable rural development in sensitive areas. *Int. J. Res. Stud. Agric. Sci. IJRSAS* 2015, 1, 21–24. Available online: www.arcjournals.org (accessed on 5 July 2022).
- [20] Entegra. Available online: <https://www.entegra.com.au/which-country-has-the-most-sheep> (accessed on 20 June 2022).